

On Some Combinatorial Action of Direct Product of Symmetric Groups S_n^6 on A_i^6 Sets

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Abstract - In this paper, we study some action of S_n^6 on A_i^6 . With Particular cases for $n = 2, 3, \dots$ and provide new combinatorial and structural insight into direct product actions of symmetric groups. Groups, Algorithms and Programming software (GAP) have been used to compute the elements of stabilizer S_n^6 . Orbit-stabiliser theorem and Cauchy-Frobenius lemma were applied to determine the number of $S_n^6(x)$ orbits and their corresponding length respectively. We established that the action is *transitive, faithful* and *imprimitive* for $n \geq 2$. Further results include explicit descriptions of point stabilizers, computation of orbit sizes using the Orbit-Stabilizer Theorem. We also established kernel of the action S_n^6 on A_i^6 , and the construction of associated suborbital graphs and Upper bounds for the diameter of the resulting graphs are obtained, we the generalized the action S_n^k for any $n \geq 2$ on Cartesian products of k - sets.

Keywords - group action, symmetric group, direct product, rank, subdegrees, association scheme.

INTRODUCTION

The study of group action revealed some important properties of algebraic systems. The invariants are extremely useful for classifying mathematical objects because they reflect the real nature of the object of study.

The rank and subdegrees of a permutation group have been studied by several group theorist. Group actions provide a framework for studying symmetry in algebraic and combinatorial structures. Orbits, stabilizers, ranks and subdegrees are fundamental invariants that reveal the internal structure of an action of the Group. Group theory and its combinatorial representations provide a clear framework for understanding symmetries in mathematics and related sciences. Among the structures that capture group actions in a visual form are orbital and suborbital graphs, which encode the orbitals of a permutation group in graph-theoretic terms.

The direct product is one of the most versatile constructions in group theory, serving as a fundamental building block in the analysis of permutation groups. It combines two groups in a hierarchical manner, yielding rich structures that exhibit imprimitive, primitive, and product-type actions. In particular, when direct products act on sets, they generate complex orbit partitions that can be studied using suborbital graphs Γ . The action of S_n^6 on A_i^6 is defined component wise by $(\delta_1, \dots, \delta_6)(a_1, \dots, a_6) = (\delta_1(a_1), \dots, \delta_6(a_6))$

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 (Group Action). A group G is said to act on the left of a set $[n]$ if for each $g \in G$ and $x \in [n]$, there exists a unique element $gx \in X$ such that for all $x \in X$ and $g_1, g_2 \in G$, $(g_1 g_2)x = g_1(g_2 x)$ and $ex = x$, where e is the identity in G .

Definition 2.2 (Orbits). The action of a group G on a set X partitions X into disjoint equivalence classes referred to as orbits or transitivity classes of action. The orbit containing $x \in X$ is denoted by $OrbG(x)$.

Definition 2.3 (Transitive). The action of a group G on a set X is said to be transitive if for all $x, y \in X$, there exists $g \in G$ such that $gx = y$. That is, the action is transitive if it results to only one orbit.

Definition 2.4 (Fixed point). Let a group G act on a non-empty set X and $g \in G$. Then the set $Fix(g) = \{x \in X : gx = x\}$ is known as the fixed-point set of g .

Definition 2.5 (Stabilizer). Let a group G act on a non-empty set X and $x \in X$. The set $G_x = \{g \in G : gx = x\}$ is known as the stabilizer of $x \in G$.

Definition 2.6 (Block and primitivity). Let the action of G on a set X be transitive. Then a block of the action is a subset $A \subseteq X$ such that either $g(A) \cap A = \emptyset$ or $g(A) = A$ for all $g \in G$. In particular X, \emptyset and all singleton subsets of X are blocks known as trivial blocks.

The action is said to be primitive if it does not have blocks other than the trivial ones; otherwise, its imprimitive

II. MAIN RESULTS

Transitivity, Faithfulness and Imprimitivity

Theorem 3.1. The action of S_n^6 on A_i^6 is transitive.

Proof. Let $x = (a_1, \dots, a_6)$ and $y = (b_1, \dots, b_6) \in T$. For each i there exists $\delta_i \in S_n$ such that $\delta_i(a_i) = b_i$. Thus x is mapped to y .

Theorem 3.2. The action of S_n^6 on A_i^6 is faithful.

Proof. If an element fixes all points, it must be trivial in every coordinate.

Theorem 3.3. The action of S_n^6 on A_i^6 is imprimitive.

Proof.
 The set $B = \{(n, n + 1, 2n + 1, 3n + 1, 4n + 1, 5n + i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ forms a nontrivial block system.

Ranks and Subdegrees

Fix $x = (1, n + 1, 2n + 1, 3n + 1, 4n + 1, 5n + 1) \in A_i^6$.

Theorem 3.4. The action S_n^6 on A_i^6 has rank 64, with subdegrees

$$1, 6(n - 1), 15(n - 1)^2, 20(n - 1)^3, 15(n - 1)^4, 6(n - 1)^5, (n - 1)^6.$$

Proof. Two elements lie in the same suborbit if they differ in the same number of coordinates. If k coordinates differ, the orbit size is $6(n - 1)^k$.

Hence the total number of suborbits is $2^6 = 64$.

Further Results and Applications

Theorem 3.5. The kernel of the action S_n^6 on A_i^6 is trivial.

Proof. An element fixing all of A_i^6 fixes every coordinate pointwise.

Theorem 3.6. For any $x \in A_i^6$,

$$|Orb_{S_n^6}(x)| = n$$

Proof. By Orbit-Stabilizer,

$$|Orb_{S_n^6}(x)| = \frac{(n!)^6}{((n-1)!)^6} = n^6$$

Theorem 3.7. For any $x \in A_i^6$
 $S_n^6(x) \cong (S_{(n-1)})^6$

Proof. Each coordinate stabilizer is isomorphic to $S_{(n-1)}$.

Suborbital Graphs

Theorem 3.8. $S_n^6 \leq Aut(\Gamma)$, where Γ is the suborbital graph of the action.

Proof. The group preserves suborbit adjacency.

Theorem 3.9. The diameter of Γ is at most 6.

Proof. Two vertices differ in at most six coordinates.

Association Schemes

Theorem 3.10. The action S_n^6 on A_i^6 induces an association scheme with 64 classes.

Proof. Each suborbit defines one relation.

Generalization

Theorem 3.11. Let S_n^k act on $A_1 \times \dots \times A_k$. Then the rank is 2^k and the subdegrees are $\binom{k}{j} (n - 1)^j$, $j = 0, \dots, k$

Table 1: Suborbit Structure

Differing Coordinates	Number of Suborbits	Subdegrees
0	1	1
1	6	$6(n - 1)$
2	15	$15(n - 1)^2$
3	20	$20(n - 1)^3$
4	15	$15(n - 1)^4$
5	6	$6(n - 1)^5$
6	1	$(n - 1)^6$

III. CONCLUSION

The action of S_n^6 on A_i^6 exhibits rich combinatorial structure. The results presented provide an explicit description of ranks, subdegrees, stabilizers and associated combinatorial objects. These findings extend naturally to direct products of arbitrary length.

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